

Social Well-Being among Scheduled Populations in Kolhapur District: A Micro-Level Geographical Analysis

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Abstract:

Welfare geography critically examines issues of inequality, social justice, and the distribution of societal benefits. In India, historical, cultural, and social hierarchies have historically led to significant regional and social deprivation. This study aims to assess the social well-being status of Scheduled Caste (SC) and Scheduled Tribe (ST) populations across sample villages in Kolhapur District. Although Kolhapur is recognized for its agro-based industrialization and holds the highest per capita income in India, the well-being of its marginalized populations remains highly unsatisfactory.

Keywords: Social Well-Being, Kolhapur District, Scheduled Population (SC/ST)

Introduction:

Geography is fundamentally the study of the environment and humans, making it natural to consider the welfare of people living on the planet. In the 1970s, the direction of Human Geography changed drastically, shifting its focus towards social problems such as poverty, hunger, crime, racial discrimination, and access to health and education. This gave rise to the welfare approach in geography, which primarily deals with issues of inequality and injustice. Welfare geography gives importance to "who gets what, where and how".

Geography is a socially relevant discipline that helps create a modern framework for micro-level enquiries. However, developing countries like India are lagging far behind in addressing these problems through intellectual and academic pursuit. In Indian society, there is a long history of social, economic, and spatial discrimination. The root cause lies in uneven resource distribution and an unjust social structure based on religion, culture, and social

hierarchy. Social well-being is normative in nature, based on the premises of needs and wants, and relates to the quality of life and habitat from a spatial perspective. Therefore, addressing the needs of various sections of people on the basis of class, ethnicity, age, gender, and caste is essential for social planning and eliminating injustice.

Study Area:

The study area for this research is the Kolhapur district in Maharashtra, India. India possesses cultural and historical diversity in each region, and Kolhapur district has its own distinct cultural and historical background. It is one of the important cities in India with respect to agriculture and industrialization. Notably, Kolhapur district has well-developed agro-based industries and holds the highest per capita income in India.

Fig. 1

Despite this overall economic progress, the well-being status of the Scheduled Caste (SC) and Scheduled Tribe (ST) population in the district is not satisfactory. Most of the scheduled population lacks educational awareness and is engaged in working as farm labour because they do not possess their own land for farming. The micro-level spatial analysis in this study is based on primary data collected from specific sample villages within the district, which include Shirol, Abdul lat, Rukadi, Mangaon, Kuditre, Shirol, Kotoli, Kale, Saravade, Walve, Sangaon, and Chikhali. Furthermore, specific remote and tribal talukas such as Hatkanagale, Shahuwadi, Gadhinglaj, Karveer, and Bhudargad are noted for poor health indicators and high child mortality rates.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To analyze the status of social well-being among the Scheduled populations in the Kolhapur district.

2. To examine the regional and social inequalities in well-being across the selected sample villages.

Database:

The study relies on both primary and secondary data sources: Primary Data: Information was collected through intensive fieldwork and primary surveys of households in 12 selected sample villages: Shirol, Abdul lat, Rukadi, Mangaon, Kuditre, Shirol, Kotoli, Kale, Saravade, Walve, Sangaon, and Chikhali. Secondary Data: Theoretical frameworks and supporting data were gathered from published books, research journals, and socio-economic abstract 2001 to 2021, Census of India 2011.

Research Methodology:

Selection of Indicators: Five major groups of indicators were selected to measure well-being: Demographic Structure: Household size, family composition, and age dependency (population below 15 and above 60). Educational Levels: Literacy rates and levels of attainment from primary to higher education. Employment Situation: Employment and unemployment rates, including agricultural labor and private sector involvement. Wealth Situation: Household income, per capita income, housing conditions, amenities, and ownership of agricultural land. Health: Availability of health facilities, malnutrition levels, child mortality rates, food insecurity, and poverty conditions.

Data Classification: The collected primary data was converted into percentages and classified into five categories to represent the level of well-being: Very High, High, Moderate, Low, and Very Low. Scoring and Ranking: An aggregate ranking system was applied to every group to calculate a well-being score. These scores were then ranked from 1 to 5 to define the

overall social well-being status of the surveyed households.

Social Well Being:

In order to have social justice/harmony, well-being is highly essential. A social lifestyle of an individual is related to well-being. While studying well-being of households of scheduled caste and scheduled tribes from sample village, demographic, education, employment, asset, health etc are being focused as fundamental aspects for well-being. Well-being is defined on the basis of status of all above aspects. By combining the data based on above aspects, collective well-being is defined. In order to define well-being, five groups are being formed like Very High, High, Moderate, Low and Very Low. An aggregate rank for every group is being defined to calculate well-being score. Then this score is ranked from 1 to 5 to explain well-being status. While defining overall social well-being status, demographic stands as an important aspect. Particularly this aspect is decided by a number of families and number of members in family. Depending upon this, while defining aggregate rank groups like very high, high, moderate, low and very low are formed. While studying demography of sample villages, overall social well-being is observed to show the moderate status of well-being which is then followed by low, high, very high, very low.

Education is also equally important while defining social well-being. The literacy level of households from sample villages is studied and analysed. While doing this, literacy rate and a number of individuals who have primary, secondary and higher secondary levels completed are being analysed. Then aggregate rank is being fixed against a total number of educated individuals. It is then again grouped under very high, high, moderate, low and very low classes. With such analysis based on aggregate rank on education level, overall social well-being show moderate well-being status which is then followed by high, very low, low and very low.

Employment is another important constraint of well-being status. Financial condition and economic status is dependent upon availability of employment. If there is ample availability of employment, the society enjoys a high and comfortable lifestyle. While fixing aggregate rank for Employment, individuals from households of sample village are being classified under various types of employment such as service, agricultural labour, farmer etc. Then the well-being status is being defined. In order to define the status very high, high, moderate, low and very low groups are formed. Most of the households from sample villages belong to low-income group and thus, the overall social well-being based on employment show moderate status which is followed by low, high, very high and very low.

Table 1 Overall Social Well- Being in Kolhapur District

Categories	Demo-graphy	Educ-ation	Emple-ment	Wealth	Health	Well Being Score	Rank
Very High	3.8	3.2	3.6	4.2	4.8	3.92	5
High	3.4	2.4	2.8	3.8	4.2	3.32	3
Moderate	1.4	2.0	1.6	2.2	2.1	1.88	1
Low	2.0	2.8	2.8	2.6	2.2	2.48	2
Very Low	4.2	4.6	4.2	2.8	1.6	3.48	4

Source: Based on the field work 2025

Health is another important constraint in the understanding of social well-being status. Generally, health depends upon income, per capita income, house, agricultural land, house amenities etc. All the above aspects are positive. Diversity is observed in surveying households from sample villages when they were surveyed for well-being status based on above aspects. They are then classified under five groups as per their very high, high, moderate, and low and very low status. Aggregate rank is then being fixed to obtain overall social well-being status of sample villages. The study shows that the overall social well-being has a moderate status which is then followed by low, very low, high and very high well-being.

Health facilities are the deciding aspect when it comes to health. Along with that, malnutrition, child mortality rate, food insecurity and poverty stand as negative sides. Depending upon all above aspects households from sample village are being classified into five groups. Aggregate rank is being fixed for every single aspect to understand well-being status of households. Then they were given low to high rank. With such most of the households are observed to belong to a moderate status group which is then followed by moderate, very low, low and then very high.

In order to define overall social well-being, demography, education, employment, wealth and health are considered as fundamental constraints. They are studied to define well-being score. Initially, the details regarding all the above aspects are being collected. Based on collected data, the aggregate rank was being fixed for every single aspect. Their aggregate value is then being confirmed. Then well-being score is obtained by having an average of all values. With such calculation, overall social well-being shows moderate status as the category is reflected in all

constraints. It is then followed by a low, high, very low and very high.

Conclusion:

In order to define well-being in sample villages in Kolhapur district, five indicators are being used. Well-being depends upon the demographic structure. It is equally depends upon educational level, employment, wealth and health. The overall social well-being is also being studied. In India, there is an astonishing inequality in social and economic conditions. Today also the population of India is divided into different groups as per social aspects and conditions. Thus we have failed to see any equality. Mainly this difference is felt in two groups i.e. poor and rich. This difference is born with economic inequality but these two groups are not only result of economic inequality. Indian caste system is one of the root causes of inequality among the people. Traditionally some castes like Mahar, Mang, Chambhar and Dhor etc. are considered socially inferior and are at the bottom of so called caste system. This caste system is one of the biggest hurdles in the development of scheduled population. In India social status depends not only on economic basis but also on social status that is caste of a person. The caste does not allow person to enjoy status of well-being psychologically. But the Indian government always tries to give justice to all the backward groups through various policies and schemes. The state and central governments have been executing various policies and schemes for the economic and social development of all such groups for the last three decades. The present chapter discusses different policies implemented by the government to rule out poverty and food insecurity. It is concluded that the joint families and members of above age 60 have shown medium well-being status.

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